

Solar and Stellar Coronal Mass Ejections

- a review of the Cool Stars 21 splinter session -

Iulia Chifu¹, Ângela R. G. Santos², Ricardo Gafeira³, Volker Bothmer¹

¹ Institute for Astrophysics and Geophysics, University of Göttingen, Germany, Friedrich-Hund-Platz 1, 37077 Göttingen, Germany

² Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciências do Espaço, Universidade do Porto, CAUP, Rua das Estrelas, PT4150-762 Porto, Portugal

³ Instituto de Astrofísica e Ciências do Espaço, Departamento de Física, Universidade de Coimbra, OGAUC, Rua do Observatório s/n, PT3040-004 Coimbra, Portugal

Abstract

Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) are the most energetic phenomena related to magnetic activity and, by impacting the interplanetary space, they can be the source of severe planetary disturbances. Solar CMEs and their sources, such as flares and filament/prominence eruptions, have been intensively observed and studied over decades. The observations of stellar CMEs and their counterpart sources are still not possible in an easy and direct manner. As a consequence, the study of stellar CMEs sources did not receive the same attention as the solar ones. Nevertheless, with the advent of high-resolution photometric space missions, the observation of white-light flares has become more easily available. Still, it has not been possible to observe stellar CMEs directly. Instead, stellar CMEs are indirectly observed to be considered a natural effect of stellar flares or prominence eruptions. The increased interest in finding habitable planets in other planetary systems triggered a high interest in understanding the possible hazardous stellar events to their orbiting planets. Within this review of the Cool Stars 21 splinter session Solar and Stellar CMEs, we make a summary of the current status of the sources of the stellar CMEs, their observations and simulations.

1 Introduction

In this proceeding paper, we make a summary of the session Solar and Stellar Coronal Mass Ejections¹ (CMEs) in the context of increased research on this subject.

From the number of publications about stellar CME, one can notice, starting in 2017, that there is a continuous increase of interest regarding the subject of stellar CMEs observations, simulations, sources, and effects on other planets. To understand more about the stellar systems in our universe, it is important to try understanding our own star, the Sun. For decades many ground and space-based observatories focused their efforts on developing instruments capable of observing solar phenomena in the greatest detail possible. Over time, these observations were extremely important in validating and constraining the theoretical models of the solar phenomena. While we can have multiple types of solar observations in all wavelengths and with high spatial and temporal sampling, it is not the same situation for stellar observations.

The solar CMEs are one of the most important phenomena affecting the heliosphere and its planetary environments, i.e. they are the major drivers of space weather (SW). SW can have adverse effects on space and ground-based technologies such as spacecraft, satellites, navigation systems, communications, pipelines, and electric power grids (Narechania *et al.*, 2021; Bothmer & Zhukov, 2007). In the case of the stellar CMEs, they can alter the atmospheres of the exoplanets, which may be disadvantageous for hosting life (Vida *et al.*, 2019). Similar to the Sun, stellar CMEs may also play an important role in mass and angular momentum loss of young

Sun-like stars (Odert *et al.*, 2017).

The following sections summarize the advancements and results presented during the splinter session Solar and Stellar CMEs. In Section 2 we make a short introduction to the solar CME subject, in Section 3, we introduce the current knowledge about the sources of the stellar CMEs, in Section 4 we present the status of the observations and simulations of the stellar CMEs, and in Section 5 we draw a couple of our conclusions.

2 Solar CMEs

CMEs are large-scale solar plasma eruptions into interplanetary space that were first detected with space-born coronagraphs in the early 1970s. Today they are observed routinely and from different vantage points, with vastly improved cadence, by telescopes onboard Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO, Domingo *et al.*, 1995), Solar Terrestrial Relation Observatory (STEREO, Kaiser *et al.*, 2008), Parker Solar Probe (PSP, Fox *et al.*, 2016) and Solar Orbiter (SO, Müller *et al.*, 2020).

In Fig. 1 we display an example of a solar CME observed during a total solar eclipse (right panel) and at the same time by the SOHO/LASCO coronagraph C2 telescope (left panel).

It took decades from the first solar CME observations to the development of the first CME simulations. In the case of the stellar CMEs, the observations are still difficult, but regarding the modelling, there is a great advantage of the existing solar CME models which can be adapted for different stars.

The solar source regions of CMEs are associated with bipolar photospheric magnetic fields and reconnection processes are often accompanied by flares and prominence eruptions.

¹<https://gafeira.wixsite.com/main>

Figure 1: A CME captured by the SOHO/LASCO C2 coronagraph (left panel) and during the solar eclipse (right panel) on the 3rd of November 2013. The solar eclipse image was captured by C. Emmannoulis and processed by M. Druckmueller (source: http://www.zam.fme.vutbr.cz/~druck/Eclipse/Ecl2013g/TSE_2013c2_ed/0-info.htm)

In some cases, flares and CMEs have comparable energies (Harra *et al.*, 2016). The stellar flares and the associated CMEs can be of the fourth order of magnitude higher than the solar ones (Harra *et al.*, 2016). The energies of strong X class flares amount to about 10^{32} ergs (Harra *et al.*, 2016). The solar prominences are formed at the site of the polarity inversion lines of the magnetic field. The prominence plasma, with typical temperatures of 8000K, is suspended above the photosphere, which is the innermost layer of the solar atmosphere. When observed as a projection on the solar disk, prominences seen in absorption are called filaments. The solar prominences are typically detected in the $H\alpha$ wavelength and He 304 Å line (Wang *et al.*, 1998), but some are also visible in the wavelengths of Fe 171 Å (Su *et al.*, 2015), or 193 Å (Schwartz *et al.*, 2015), which are formed at the temperature of several MK. The coronagraph instruments take images of the solar corona in visible light and of the prominence material when a CME occurs. Many eruptive prominences triggering CMEs are formed in the so-called quiet Sun, where the magnetic fields are at least one order of magnitude lower than the ones in the active regions. The active region flares responsible for the CMEs have an underlying photospheric magnetic field of the order of kG.

The CMEs observed in the coronagraph imaging with an angular width² (AW) of less than 15° are called narrow CMEs (Mandrini *et al.*, 2005, and references therein) while all the rest are called normal CMEs. The narrow CMEs are believed to be related to small-scale magnetic flux rope (SMFRs) eruptions on the Sun. Small and narrow CMEs can have their origin in bright bipolar regions. They can also come from quiet Sun regions without any apparent underlying trace (Robbrecht *et al.*, 2009), but they can also have their source at the top point of the coronal helmet streamers (Rouillard *et al.*, 2011).

The exact trigger mechanism of CMEs is still under debate. It has been observed that most of the strongest CMEs originate in the magnetic inversion polarity line under low plasma beta conditions (Sharykin *et al.*, 2018). Previous stud-

ies indicate they are driven by free magnetic energy in non-potential fields (DeVore & Antiochos, 2005). This free energy can be originated by convection in the photosphere that shear and twist the magnetic field (Klimchuk & Sturrock, 1992) or brought by the convection zone from dipper layers (Leka *et al.*, 1996). The eruption is then caused by an imbalance or loss in the magnetic equilibrium (Forbes, 2000), though the processes that occur before and during the eruption are still unclear (Green, 2019). In the corona, torus instability (Démoulin & Aulanier, 2010) and magnetic reconnection (Vršnak, 2016) are the two main physical mechanisms responsible for the build-up of magnetic flux ropes and their energetic ejection (CMEs) in the interplanetary space.

As this paper is not a review of the CMEs, we would like to guide the reader towards some of the more comprehensible reviews on the subject of the CMEs (Webb & Howard, 2012; Chen, 2011; Forbes, 2000; Kahler, 1992; Hudson *et al.*, 2006; Vourlidis *et al.*, 2019).

3 Stellar CME sources

In the Sun, flares are often accompanied by CMEs (e.g. Andrews, 2003; Hathaway, 2015). One may expect a similar connection between flares and CMEs in other cool stars. Flares are a sudden release of magnetic energy and can be detected in a wide range of wavelengths from radio to X-rays (e.g. Benz, 2008; Güdel *et al.*, 2002; Gryciuk *et al.*, 2017; Brasseur *et al.*, 2019, 2022; Getman & Feigelson, 2021; Rigney *et al.*, 2022).

In the era of planet-hunting photometric space missions, such as *Kepler* (Borucki *et al.*, 2010), *Kepler/K2* (Howell *et al.*, 2014), and TESS (Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite; Ricker *et al.*, 2014), it has been possible to detect hundreds of thousands of white-light flare events in thousands of stars (e.g. Davenport, 2016; Yang & Liu, 2019; Günther *et al.*, 2020; Tu *et al.*, 2020; Stelzer *et al.*, 2022). In white-light solar and stellar flares are seen as a sudden increase in stellar brightness, characterized by a fast rise and a slow exponential decay (e.g. Davenport *et al.*, 2014; Pitkin *et al.*, 2014; Kashapova *et al.*, 2021; Mendoza *et al.*, 2022; Howard, 2022; Oláh *et al.*, 2022). Some of the observed events are complex, with over-

²defined as the angle at the Sun centre between the two lateral CME boundaries as seen in the coronagraph

lapping flares (e.g. Davenport *et al.*, 2014; Maehara *et al.*, 2015; Howard & MacGregor, 2022; Oláh *et al.*, 2022). Also, flares can display quasi-periodic pulsations, which are variations in the flare emission (e.g. Parks & Winckler, 1969; Mathioudakis *et al.*, 2003; Nakariakov *et al.*, 2018; Broomhall *et al.*, 2019; Howard & MacGregor, 2022). The precision and cadence of the observations play an crucial role in the detection and characterization of stellar flares (e.g. Yang *et al.*, 2018; Davenport *et al.*, 2020; Gilbert *et al.*, 2022; Howard & MacGregor, 2022). Namely, low signal-to-noise ratio and long cadence hamper the detection of small energy flares. Furthermore, in comparison with short cadence, long cadence leads to a severe underestimation of the amplitudes and, consequently, energies and an overestimation of the flare duration.

In spite of the similarities and analogies between the solar and stellar flares, *Kepler* revealed that superflares, with energies orders of magnitude larger than those of solar events, are common in other stars (e.g. Maehara *et al.*, 2012; Shibayama *et al.*, 2013; Namekata *et al.*, 2017; Notsu *et al.*, 2019). While superflares are more common among young fast rotators, they are still detected in G dwarfs (dwarf meaning main-sequence star) with similar surface rotation to the Sun³ (e.g. Notsu *et al.*, 2019; Yang & Liu, 2019; Okamoto *et al.*, 2021). Nevertheless, whether such extreme events could occur in the present Sun is still under debate in the community. Moreover, the occurrence rate decreases with the flare energy (e.g. Lacy *et al.*, 1976; Pettersen *et al.*, 1984; Maehara *et al.*, 2015; Notsu *et al.*, 2019; Davenport *et al.*, 2020; Gilbert *et al.*, 2022), therefore low energy events tend to occur more frequently.

While in the main-sequence, flare energies and occurrence rates tend to decrease as stars evolve, evolved red giants seem to exhibit longer and more energetic flares in comparison with dwarfs (e.g. Balona, 2015; Oláh *et al.*, 2022). Flare duration and energy are also related, with high energy events lasting longer (e.g. Pettersen, 1989; Maehara *et al.*, 2015). In addition to the stellar evolutionary stage, the properties of the flare events also depend on the spectral type. In particular, M dwarfs tend to exhibit larger flare rates than hotter solar-like stars (e.g. Davenport, 2016; Feinstein *et al.*, 2020; Günther *et al.*, 2020; Tu *et al.*, 2020; Howard, 2022).

In the Sun, CMEs are also often associated with eruptive filaments or prominences (e.g. Webb *et al.*, 1976; Munro *et al.*, 1979; Gopalswamy *et al.*, 2003). Evidence for filament eruptions have been reported over the years for K and M dwarfs (e.g. Houdebine *et al.*, 1990; Vida *et al.*, 2016; Fuhrmeister *et al.*, 2018; Honda *et al.*, 2018; Vida *et al.*, 2019; Maehara *et al.*, 2021; Muheki *et al.*, 2020a,b). This has been possible in particular through the detection of blue asymmetries in the hydrogen Balmer lines during flare events. The blue asymmetry corresponds to an excess of emission in the blue wing of the lines, which can be associated with the rising of plasma. Recently, the first evidence for an eruptive filament in a G-type star was reported by Namekata *et al.* (2021). The filament eruption was linked to a superflare in EK Draconis, a young G dwarf, and it is plausible that a stellar CME occurred. Indeed, simultaneous observations by the space-telescope TESS (photometry) and by two ground-based telescopes (spectroscopy), revealed a superflare followed by an enhanced absorption in H α . The H α absorption component suffered a blue shift, which gradually decreased, and then a

red shift. This behaviour in H α is consistent with the observations of solar eruptive filaments, showing the signature of cool plasma first quickly rising, i.e. moving towards the observer, and then partially falling back (Namekata *et al.*, 2021). The authors also concluded that there is a high probability that this event was accompanied by a CME. The case of EK Draconis is of particular interest as it is considered to be a "young Sun".

The flare occurrence rates and flare energies of stars of different spectral types and evolutionary states may provide important clues to help understand the evolution of stellar magnetic activity. Flare occurrence rates can also enable the detection and characterization of long-term magnetic activity cycles. However, as discussed above, flare events are more frequent in M dwarfs, which might have great implications, especially if associated with stellar CMEs, in the habitability of the planets orbiting M dwarfs. Furthermore, flares may hamper the detection and characterization of planetary systems (e.g. Kipping *et al.*, 2017; Gilbert *et al.*, 2022). We note that this impact by flares, is in addition to the impact by other signatures related to magnetic activity, including rotational modulation, which also hides or resembles the planetary signals, leading to false exoplanet detections or hampering their detection (e.g. Berta *et al.*, 2012; Vanderburg *et al.*, 2016; Newton *et al.*, 2016).

4 Observations and simulations of stellar CMEs

As mentioned before, contrary to solar CMEs, stellar CMEs are more difficult to observe and model. However, the existing solar CME models can be adapted for stellar CMEs observed at other stars. Direct observations of the stellar CMEs are not yet possible due to the spatial resolution of the current instruments. A couple of methods are already employed to indirectly observe possible manifestations of them. One of the most used methods to identify the existence of stellar CME is the analysis of the spectroscopic time series of stars where stellar CMEs can be identified in the Doppler signature seen mainly in Balmer lines (Odert *et al.*, 2020). The ejected material appears as a blue-wing enhancement of the line (Vida *et al.*, 2019). From the analysis of more than 5500 spectra, Vida *et al.* (2019) identified 478 line asymmetries. While the authors assumed that the ejected stellar plasma causes the line asymmetries, they did admit that the exact nature of the observed phenomena cannot be known with certainty. Using far-ultraviolet spectrum, Leitzinger *et al.* (2011) searched for indications of stellar mass ejections. From the light curve analysis of the stellar objects, they identified flare signatures. In one of the cases, a blue wing enhancement in the spectrum after a flare event was observed and associated with a mass ejection (Leitzinger *et al.*, 2011). For the identification of CMEs in the symmetries of the Balmer lines, Koller *et al.* (2021) performed an automatic search in the spectral line profiles of 630 000 stars. They could identify only six CME candidates for which they estimated the mass and velocity. From the spectrum of a giant star, Argiroffi *et al.* (2019) detected a flare-CME couple in the blueshift of the O VIII spectral line. They were also able to derive the mass and kinetic energy of the stellar CME. The red supergiant, Begeuse, has been observed for decades. From recent observations, (Dupree *et al.*, 2022) concluded that in 2020 occurred a surface mass ejection which had an impact on the

³In this regime surface rotation is considered as a proxy for stellar age as stars spin down as they evolve (e.g. Skumanich, 1972; Barnes, 2003).

Figure 2: Snapshot of a stellar CME simulation performed by Alvarado-Gómez *et al.* (2019)

photospheric average temperatures, on the photometric oscillations, the pulsation frequency in the optical and radial velocity and most probably produced a substantial mass outflow. From the optical spectroscopical observations of the EK Draconis, Namekata *et al.* (2021) identified evidence of a stellar prominence eruption which was associated with a flare (see Section 3). They concluded that the eruptive prominence from the EK Draconis evolved in a stellar CME.

On the Sun, photospheric vector magnetic field is derived from daily observations by the Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI, Schou *et al.*, 2012) instrument on board Solar Dynamic Observatory (SDO), and during specific times by the Polarimetric and Helioseismic Imager (PHI, Solanki *et al.*, 2020) instrument onboard SO. In the solar corona, the vector magnetic field is difficult to measure. On other stars than the Sun, deriving the magnetic field at the stellar surface is a challenging task as their magnetic fields are difficult to resolve Brown *et al.* (1991). With the Zeeman Doppler Imaging (ZDI) technique, a 2D vector distribution of the surface magnetic field can be derived by considering observations from many different rotational phases (Rosén *et al.*, 2015; Brown *et al.*, 1991).

Information on the magnetic field in the stellar atmosphere is without a doubt an important aspect of understanding the CMEs triggering mechanisms and evolution. For estimating the magnetic field in the upper layers of the Sun, one needs to apply magnetic field extrapolation methods. Some methods are using only the radial component of the magnetic field like potential field (Altschuler & Newkirk, 1969; Wang & Sheeley, 1992) and the linear force-free field Gary (1989); Wiegmann & Sakurai (2021) method, while other methods require as bottom boundary the vector magnetic field, as some of the nonlinear force-free field methods (Wheatland *et al.*, 2000; Wiegmann, 2004; Wiegmann & Sakurai, 2012), magneto-hydrostatics methods Zhu *et al.* (2022).

By applying potential field extrapolations to the ZDI maps of ten stars, Waugh *et al.* (2021) derived the stellar coronal magnetic fields and studied the location where the prominences may form and determined their equilibrium points. A study by Namekata *et al.* (2021) indicates that an eruptive stellar prominence can be ten times larger than the typical solar prominences. The eruption of such large stellar promi-

nences can influence substantially the dynamics of the star by decreasing its rotation rate, and it can also be a source for enhanced stellar wind conditions (Waugh *et al.*, 2021).

Contrasting with stellar flares, the detections of stellar CMEs are limited. On one hand, the lack of CME reports may be related to observational biases and limitations. On the other hand, it may be of physical origin, namely, it can be related to the suppression of the mechanism responsible for CMEs. One of the CME triggering mechanisms is the torus instability of the magnetic flux ropes in the context of strong magnetic fields. One approach for investigating the stellar flux-rope (in)stability was taken by Sun *et al.* (2022) who studied different scenarios required for a stellar eruption to take place triggered by the instability of a torus-like flux rope. Under the assumption that the CMEs have their source in the torus instability flux-ropes, (Sun *et al.*, 2022) shows that the instability zone is influenced by the stellar spot size, the magnetic field strength and the source surface radius. From their results, Sun *et al.* (2022) suggest that the low CME rate on cool stars might be due to the presence of an extended zone of stability of the torus like flux-ropes. Also, they suggest that this inhibition might be particularly important for stars with large active regions or strong global magnetic fields.

From previous solar physics research (Harrison & Lyons, 2000), it was observed the so-called coronal dimming, i.e sudden decrease in the EUV and X-ray emission in the low solar corona. A recent study, presented in Veronig *et al.* (2021), reports indications for the occurrence of stellar CMEs through dimming detection associated with flares on cool stars. Another direction for stellar CME identification, suggested by Alvarado-Gómez *et al.* (2020), is the detection of type II radio bursts as they often occur during the development of an outward propagating CME-driven shock.

MHD modelling of the stellar CMEs is one of the natural approaches to grasp into the physics of the CMEs on other stars. The theoretical models developed for explaining the initiation and evolution of the solar CMEs have been developed already over several decades (Forbes, 2000). Contrary, the modelling of stellar CME is still at its beginnings. Stellar CMEs simulations were reported in couple of studies by Alvarado-Gómez *et al.* (2018, 2019, 2020, 2022). They used

solar 3D magneto-hydrodynamic (MHD) models and in one of their studies, they showed that the stellar large-scale magnetic field can suppress some CMEs, a result supported also by the modelling of Sun *et al.* (2022). One such result of a stellar CME modelling we show in Fig. 2 obtained by Alvarado-Gómez *et al.* (2019).

By adding a flux-rope eruption model to their 3D MHD model, they obtain CME events for a stellar M-dwarf simulation (Alvarado-Gómez *et al.*, 2020). They also presented various consequences of the CME magnetic-suppression process in active M-dwarf stars. One of the simulation results was that the global behaviour in each CME event revealed that the shock formation region is much different compared to the average location observed in the Sun (Alvarado-Gómez *et al.*, 2020). The result of the simulation showed that the location of the stellar CMEs shock can be formed up to 10 times higher above the surface than the average location for solar CMEs.

The propagation and evolution of a CME have important implications for the nearby environment. By applying an MHD simulation, Menezes *et al.* (2020) investigated the trajectory of a CME from the Sun and from the Kepler-63 star. From the sun-stellar CME comparison, they concluded that in the conditions of three times stronger magnetic field compared with the solar one, the CMEs from Kepler-63 would undergo higher deflections and rotation.

5 Conclusions

Coronal mass ejections in the Sun have been studied for decades. Still, the physical mechanisms behind these events are unclear and different scenarios are under consideration. Efforts have been made in order to detect CMEs in stars other than the Sun, as well as their indirect evidence related for example to filament/prominence eruptions. While the lack of stellar CMEs detection might result from observational limitations, it has been considered that it might be physical in nature, with strong large-scale fields possibly playing a central role in CME suppression. In contrast to stellar CMEs, stellar flares are superflares that have been detected and characterized for thousands of cool stars.

Flares and CMEs can represent important contributions to driving space weather conditions. That can affect us due to the negative aspects that such events can cause in our technological way of living since they can cause disturbance in communications, satellite positioning systems and the electrical grid disruption in case of an extreme event. Those events can also be observed on other stars and planetary systems that consequently can affect the habitability of other worlds, for example, by changing the chemistry of their atmospheres or stripping them (e.g. Vidal-Madjar *et al.*, 2003; Lecavelier Des Etangs *et al.*, 2010; Jakosky *et al.*, 2018; Airapetian *et al.*, 2020; Chen *et al.*, 2021; Konings *et al.*, 2022; Hazra *et al.*, 2022; Alvarado-Gómez *et al.*, 2022). Indeed, the increasing number of known exoplanets, in particular in the so-called habitable zone, has led to an increasing interest in understanding star-planet interactions and the environment around stars (e.g. Günther *et al.*, 2020; Howard, 2022; Ilin & Poppenhaeger, 2022; Feinstein *et al.*, 2022; Garraffo *et al.*, 2022; Ridgway *et al.*, 2023). On one hand, studying Sun-like stars can help us to better understand our own planetary system and the conditions allowing for life to be prompted and sustained. On the other hand, M dwarfs are of notable appeal

to the community (e.g. Kay *et al.*, 2016; Howard *et al.*, 2018; Günther *et al.*, 2020; Gilbert *et al.*, 2022; Ilin & Poppenhaeger, 2022; Stelzer *et al.*, 2022). They are abundant and the detection of small Earth-like planets are in principle easier thanks to their relative size and mass. Moreover, it is easier to detect planets in the habitable zone, i.e. where water can exist in the liquid form at the planet's surface, as it is located closer to the star in comparison to hotter stars (Kaltenegger, 2017, and references therein). Although one easily makes the analogy between solar and stellar CMEs, the processes behind them and their consequences, Alvarado-Gómez *et al.* (2022) raised an important point which is direct solar extrapolations should be avoided and realistic stellar properties must be considered.

Kepler observations provided a unique opportunity for stellar physics allowing us to characterize phenomena related to magnetic activity, including stellar flares in thousands of stars. While TESS observations are shorter-term and present a lower signal-to-noise ratio (see implications for flare detection and characterization in e.g. Davenport *et al.*, 2020), one of the advantages of TESS targets is that they are brighter and, thus, high-quality and high-resolution ground base observations are possible. As a result one can perform simultaneous observations in different wavelengths, allowing for example to search for evidence of filament eruptions and potentially CMEs (e.g. Maehara *et al.*, 2021; Namekata *et al.*, 2021). Future PLANetary Transits and Oscillations (PLATO; Rauer *et al.*, 2014) mission will also observe bright targets for relatively long time spans. Consequently and given the scientific goals of the PLATO mission, PLATO stars and planetary systems are expected to be well characterized. In this context, PLATO might contribute to a significant step forward in our understanding of stellar magnetic activity, including flares and CMEs and their mechanisms.

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank to all of the contributors to the Solar and Stellar CMEs session. I.C. and V.B. acknowledges the support of the Coronagraphic German and US Solar Probe Plus Survey (CGAUSS) project for WISPR by the German Aerospace Center (DLR) under grant 50OL1901 as a national contribution to the Parker Solar Probe mission. A.R.G.S. and R.G. acknowledges the support from the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT) through national funds and FEDER through COMPETE2020 (UIDB/04434/2020 & UIDP/04434/2020). A.R.G.S. also acknowledges the support from the FCT through the work contract No. 2020.02480.CEECIND/CP1631/CT0001.

References

- Airapetian, V. S., Barnes, R., Cohen, O., Collinson, G. A., Danchi, W. C., *et al.* 2020, IJAsB, 19, 136.
- Altschuler, M. D. & Newkirk, G. 1969, SoPh, 9, 131.
- Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Drake, J. J., Cohen, O., Fraschetti, F., Garraffo, C., *et al.* 2022, Astron. Nachr., 343, e10100.
- Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Drake, J. J., Cohen, O., Moschou, S. P., & Garraffo, C. 2018, ApJ, 862, 93.
- Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Drake, J. J., Fraschetti, F., Garraffo, C., Cohen, O., *et al.* 2020, ApJ, 895, 47.
- Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Drake, J. J., Moschou, S. P., Garraffo, C., Cohen, O., *et al.* 2019, ApJL, 884, L13.
- Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Cohen, O., Drake, J. J., Fraschetti, F., Poppenhaeger, K., *et al.* 2022, ApJ, 928, 147.

- Andrews, M. 2003, *SoPh*, 218, 261.
- Argiroffi, C., Reale, F., Drake, J. J., Ciaravella, A., Testa, P., *et al.* 2019, *Nature Astronomy*, 3, 742.
- Balona, L. A. 2015, *MNRAS*, 447, 2714.
- Barnes, S. A. 2003, *ApJ*, 586, 464.
- Benz, A. O. 2008, *Living Reviews in Solar Physics*, 5, 1.
- Berta, Z. K., Irwin, J., Charbonneau, D., Burke, C. J., & Falco, E. E. 2012, *AJ*, 144, 145.
- Borucki, W. J., Koch, D., Basri, G., Batalha, N., Brown, T., *et al.* 2010, *Science*, 327, 977.
- Bothmer, V. & Zhukov, A. 2007, In *Space Weather- Physics and Effects*, edited by V. Bothmer & I. A. Daglis, p. 31.
- Brasseur, C. E., Osten, R. A., & Fleming, S. W. 2019, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 883, 88.
- Brasseur, C. E., Osten, R. A., Tristan, I. I., & Kowalski, A. F. 2022, *Constraints on Stellar Flare Energy Ratios in the NUV and Optical From a Multiwavelength Study of GALEX and Kepler Flare Stars*. Tech. rep., arXiv:2212.08696.
- Broomhall, A.-M., Thomas, A. E. L., Pugh, C. E., Pye, J. P., & Rosen, S. R. 2019, *A&A*, 629, A147.
- Brown, S. F., Donati, J. F., Rees, D. E., & Semel, M. 1991, *A&A*, 250, 463.
- Chen, H., Zhan, Z., Youngblood, A., Wolf, E. T., Feinstein, A. D., *et al.* 2021, *Nature Astronomy*, 5, 298.
- Chen, P. F. 2011, *Living Reviews in Solar Physics*, 8, 1.
- Davenport, J. R. A. 2016, *ApJ*, 829, 23.
- Davenport, J. R. A., Hawley, S. L., Hebb, L., Wisniewski, J. P., Kowalski, A. F., *et al.* 2014, *ApJ*, 797, 122.
- Davenport, J. R. A., Mendoza, G. T., & Hawley, S. L. 2020, *AJ*, 160, 36.
- Démoulin, P. & Aulanier, G. 2010, *ApJ*, 718, 1388.
- DeVore, C. R. & Antiochos, S. K. 2005, *The Astrophysical Journal*, 628, 1031.
- Domingo, V., Fleck, B., & Poland, A. I. 1995, *SoPh*, 162, 1.
- Dupree, A. K., Strassmeier, K. G., Calderwood, T., Granzer, T., Weber, M., *et al.* 2022, *ApJ*, 936, 18.
- Feinstein, A. D., France, K., Youngblood, A., Duvvuri, G. M., Teal, D. J., *et al.* 2022, *AJ*, 164, 110.
- Feinstein, A. D., Montet, B. T., Ansdell, M., Nord, B., Bean, J. L., *et al.* 2020, *AJ*, 160, 219.
- Forbes, T. G. 2000, , 105, 23153.
- Fox, N. J., Velli, M. C., Bale, S. D., Decker, R., Driesman, A., *et al.* 2016, *SSRv*, 204, 7.
- Fuhrmeister, B., Czesla, S., Schmitt, J. H. M. M., Jeffers, S. V., Caballero, J. A., *et al.* 2018, *A&A*, 615, A14.
- Garraffo, C., Alvarado-Gómez, J. D., Cohen, O., & Drake, J. J. 2022, *ApJ*, 941, L8.
- Gary, G. A. 1989, *ApJS*, 69, 323.
- Getman, K. V. & Feigelson, E. D. 2021, *ApJ*, 916, 32.
- Gilbert, E. A., Barclay, T., Quintana, E. V., Walkowicz, L. M., Vega, L. D., *et al.* 2022, *AJ*, 163, 147.
- Gopalswamy, N., Shimojo, M., Lu, W., Yashiro, S., Shibasaki, K., *et al.* 2003, *ApJ*, 586, 562.
- Green, L. 2019, In *Solar Heliospheric and Interplanetary Environment (SHINE 2019)*, p. 160.
- Gryciuk, M., Siarkowski, M., Sylwester, J., Gburek, S., Podgorski, P., *et al.* 2017, *SoPh*, 292, 77.
- Günther, M. N., Zhan, Z., Seager, S., Rimmer, P. B., Ranjan, S., *et al.* 2020, *AJ*, 159, 60.
- Güdel, M., Audard, M., Skinner, S. L., & Horvath, M. I. 2002, *ApJ*, 580, L73.
- Harra, L. K., Schrijver, C. J., Janvier, M., Toriumi, S., Hudson, H., *et al.* 2016, *SoPh*, 291, 1761.
- Harrison, R. A. & Lyons, M. 2000, *A&A*, 358, 1097.
- Hathaway, D. H. 2015, *Living Reviews in Solar Physics*, 12, 4.
- Hazra, G., Vidotto, A. A., Carolan, S., Villarreal D'Angelo, C., & Manchester, W. 2022, *MNRAS*, 509, 5858.
- Honda, S., Notsu, Y., Namekata, K., Notsu, S., Maehara, H., *et al.* 2018, *PASJ*, 70, 62.
- Houdebine, E. R., Foing, B. H., & Rodono, M. 1990, *A&A*, 238, 249.
- Howard, W. S. 2022, *MNRAS*, 512, L60.
- Howard, W. S. & MacGregor, M. A. 2022, *ApJ*, 926, 204.
- Howard, W. S., Tilley, M. A., Corbett, H., Youngblood, A., Loyd, R. O. P., *et al.* 2018, *ApJ*, 860, L30. ISSN 0004-637X.
- Howell, S. B., Sobeck, C., Haas, M., Still, M., Barclay, T., *et al.* 2014, *PASP*, 126, 398.
- Hudson, H. S., Bougeret, J. L., & Burkepile, J. 2006, *SSRv*, 123, 13.
- Ilin, E. & Poppenhaeger, K. 2022, *MNRAS*, 513, 4579.
- Jakosky, B. M., Brain, D., Chaffin, M., Curry, S., Deighan, J., *et al.* 2018, *Icarus*, 315, 146.
- Kahler, S. W. 1992, *ARA&A*, 30, 113.
- Kaiser, M. L., Kucera, T. A., Davila, J. M., St. Cyr, O. C., Guhathakurta, M., *et al.* 2008, *SSRv*, 136, 5.
- Kaltenegger, L. 2017, *ARA&A*, 55, 433.
- Kashapova, L. K., Broomhall, A.-M., Larionova, A. I., Kupriyanova, E. G., & Motyk, I. D. 2021, *MNRAS*, 502, 3922.
- Kay, C., Opher, M., & Kornbleuth, M. 2016, *ApJ*, 826, 195.
- Kipping, D. M., Cameron, C., Hartman, J. D., Davenport, J. R. A., Matthews, J. M., *et al.* 2017, *AJ*, 153, 93.
- Klimchuk, J. A. & Sturrock, P. A. 1992, *ApJ*, 385, 344.
- Koller, F., Leitzinger, M., Temmer, M., Odert, P., Beck, P. G., *et al.* 2021, *A&A*, 646, A34.
- Konings, T., Baeyens, R., & Decin, L. 2022, *A&A*, 667, A15.
- Lacy, C. H., Moffett, T. J., & Evans, D. S. 1976, *ApJS*, 30, 85.
- Lecavelier Des Etangs, A., Ehrenreich, D., Vidal-Madjar, A., Ballester, G. E., Désert, J.-M., *et al.* 2010, *A&A*, 514, A72.
- Leitzinger, M., Odert, P., Ribas, I., Hanslmeier, A., Lammer, H., *et al.* 2011, *A&A*, 536, A62.
- Leka, K. D., Canfield, R. C., McClymont, A. N., & van Driel-Gesztelyi, L. 1996, *ApJ*, 462, 547.
- Maehara, H., Notsu, Y., Namekata, K., Honda, S., Kowalski, A. F., *et al.* 2021, *PASJ*, 73, 44.
- Maehara, H., Shibayama, T., Notsu, S., Notsu, Y., Nagao, T., *et al.* 2012, *Nature*, 485, 478.
- Maehara, H., Shibayama, T., Notsu, Y., Notsu, S., Honda, S., *et al.* 2015, *EP&S*, 67, 59.
- Mandrini, C. H., Pohjolainen, S., Dasso, S., Green, L. M., Démoulin, P., *et al.* 2005, *A&A*, 434, 725.
- Mathioudakis, M., Seiradakis, J. H., Williams, D. R., Avgoloupis, S., Bloomfield, D. S., *et al.* 2003, *A&A*, 403, 1101.
- Mendoza, G. T., Davenport, J. R. A., Agol, E., Jackman, J. A. G., & Hawley, S. L. 2022, *AJ*, 164, 17.
- Menezes, F., Netto, Y., Kay, C., Opher, M., & Valio, A. 2020, In *Solar and Stellar Magnetic Fields: Origins and Manifestations*, edited by A. Kosovichev, S. Strassmeier, & M. Jardine, vol. 354, pp. 421–425.
- Muheki, P., Guenther, E. W., Mutabazi, T., & Jurua, E. 2020a, *A&A*, 637, A13.
- Muheki, P., Guenther, E. W., Mutabazi, T., & Jurua, E. 2020b, *MNRAS*, 499, 5047.
- Müller, D., St. Cyr, O. C., Zouganelis, I., Gilbert, H. R., Marsden, R., *et al.* 2020, *A&A*, 642, A1.

- Munro, R. H., Gosling, J. T., Hildner, E., MacQueen, R. M., Poland, A. I., *et al.* 1979, *SoPh*, 61, 201.
- Nakariakov, V. M., Anfinogentov, S., Storozhenko, A. A., Kurochkin, E. A., Bogod, V. M., *et al.* 2018, *ApJ*, 859, 154.
- Namekata, K., Maehara, H., Honda, S., Notsu, Y., Okamoto, S., *et al.* 2021, *Nature Astronomy*, 6, 241.
- Namekata, K., Sakaue, T., Watanabe, K., Asai, A., Maehara, H., *et al.* 2017, *ApJ*, 851, 91.
- Narechania, N. M., Nikolić, L., Freret, L., De Sterck, H., & Groth, C. P. T. 2021, *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate*, 11, 8.
- Newton, E. R., Irwin, J., Charbonneau, D., Berta-Thompson, Z. K., & Dittmann, J. A. 2016, *ApJL*, 821, L19.
- Notsu, Y., Maehara, H., Honda, S., Hawley, S. L., Davenport, J. R. A., *et al.* 2019, *ApJ*, 876, 58.
- Odert, P., Leitzinger, M., Guenther, E. W., & Heinzel, P. 2020, *MNRAS*, 494, 3766.
- Odert, P., Leitzinger, M., Hanslmeier, A., & Lammer, H. 2017, *MNRAS*, 472, 876.
- Okamoto, S., Notsu, Y., Maehara, H., Namekata, K., Honda, S., *et al.* 2021, *ApJ*, 906, 72.
- Oláh, K., Seli, B., Kóvári, Z., Kriskovics, L., & Vida, K. 2022, *A&A*, 668, A101.
- Parks, G. K. & Winckler, J. R. 1969, *ApJ*, 155, L117.
- Pettersen, B. R. 1989, *SoPh*, 121, 299.
- Pettersen, B. R., Coleman, L. A., & Evans, D. S. 1984, *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement Series*, 54, 375.
- Pitkin, M., Williams, D., Fletcher, L., & Grant, S. D. T. 2014, *MNRAS*, 445, 2268.
- Rauer, H., Catala, C., Aerts, C., Appourchaux, T., Benz, W., *et al.* 2014, *Exp. Astron.*, 38, 249.
- Ricker, G. R., Winn, J. N., Vanderspek, R., Latham, D. W., Bakos, G. Á., *et al.* 2014, In *Space Telescopes and Instrumentation 2014: Optical, Infrared, and Millimeter Wave*, edited by J. Oschmann, Jacobus M., M. Clampin, G. G. Fazio, & H. A. MacEwen, *Society of Photo-Optical Instrumentation Engineers (SPIE) Conference Series*, vol. 9143, p. 914320.
- Ridgway, R. J., Zamyatina, M., Mayne, N. J., Manners, J., Lambert, F. H., *et al.* 2023, *MNRAS*, 518, 2472.
- Rigney, J., Ramsay, G., Carley, E. P., Doyle, J. G., Gallagher, P. T., *et al.* 2022, *MNRAS*, 516, 540.
- Robbrecht, E., Patsourakos, S., & Vourlidas, A. 2009, *ApJ*, 701, 283.
- Rosén, L., Kochukhov, O., & Wade, G. A. 2015, *ApJ*, 805, 169.
- Rouillard, A. P., Odstrčil, D., Sheeley, N. R., Tylka, A., Vourlidas, A., *et al.* 2011, *ApJ*, 735, 7.
- Schou, J., Scherrer, P. H., Bush, R. I., Wachter, R., Couvidat, S., *et al.* 2012, *SoPh*, 275, 229.
- Schwartz, P., Heinzel, P., Kotrč, P., Fárnik, F., Kupryakov, Y. A., *et al.* 2015, *A&A*, 574, A62.
- Sharykin, I. N., Zimovets, I. V., Myshyakov, I. I., & Meshalkina, N. S. 2018, *ApJ*, 864, 156.
- Shibayama, T., Maehara, H., Notsu, S., Notsu, Y., Nagao, T., *et al.* 2013, *ApJS*, 209, 5.
- Skumanich, A. 1972, *ApJ*, 171, 565.
- Solanki, S. K., del Toro Iniesta, J. C., Woch, J., Gandorfer, A., Hirzberger, J., *et al.* 2020, *A&A*, 642, A11.
- Stelzer, B., Caramazza, M., Raetz, S., Argiroffi, C., & Coffaro, M. 2022, *A&A*, 667, L9.
- Su, Y., McCauley, P., van Ballegooijen, A., Ji, H., Reeves, K., *et al.* 2015, In *IAU General Assembly*, vol. 29, p. 2256101.
- Sun, X., Török, T., & DeRosa, M. L. 2022, *MNRAS*, 509, 5075.
- Tu, Z.-L., Yang, M., Zhang, Z. J., & Wang, F. Y. 2020, *ApJ*, 890, 46.
- Vanderburg, A., Plavchan, P., Johnson, J. A., Ciardi, D. R., Swift, J., *et al.* 2016, *MNRAS*, 459, 3565.
- Veronig, A. M., Odert, P., Leitzinger, M., Dissauer, K., Fleck, N. C., *et al.* 2021, *Nature Astronomy*, 5, 697.
- Vida, K., Kriskovics, L., Oláh, K., Leitzinger, M., Odert, P., *et al.* 2016, *A&A*, 590, A11.
- Vida, K., Leitzinger, M., Kriskovics, L., Seli, B., Odert, P., *et al.* 2019, *A&A*, 623, A49.
- Vidal-Madjar, A., Lecavelier des Etangs, A., Désert, J. M., Ballester, G. E., Ferlet, R., *et al.* 2003, *Nature*, 422, 143.
- Vourlidas, A., Patsourakos, S., & Savani, N. P. 2019, *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London Series A*, 377, 20180096.
- Vršnak, B. 2016, *Astronomische Nachrichten*, 337, 1002.
- Wang, H., Chae, J., Gurman, J. B., & Kucera, T. A. 1998, *SoPh*, 183, 91.
- Wang, Y. M. & Sheeley, J., N. R. 1992, *ApJ*, 392, 310.
- Waugh, R. F. P., Jardine, M. M., Morin, J., & Donati, J. F. 2021, *MNRAS*, 505, 5104.
- Webb, D. F. & Howard, T. A. 2012, *Living Reviews in Solar Physics*, 9, 3.
- Webb, D. F., Krieger, A. S., & Rust, D. M. 1976, *SoPh*, 48, 159.
- Wheatland, M. S., Sturrock, P. A., & Roumeliotis, G. 2000, *ApJ*, 540, 1150.
- Wiegelmann, T. 2004, *SoPh*, 219, 87.
- Wiegelmann, T. & Sakurai, T. 2012, *LRSP*, 9, 5.
- Wiegelmann, T. & Sakurai, T. 2021, *Living Reviews in Solar Physics*, 18, 1.
- Yang, H. & Liu, J. 2019, *ApJS*, 241, 29.
- Yang, H., Liu, J., Qiao, E., Zhang, H., Gao, Q., *et al.* 2018, *ApJ*, 859, 87.
- Zhu, X., Neukirch, T., & Wiegelmann, T. 2022, *Science China Technological Sciences*, 65, 1710–1726.